

Human Performance Improvements: Key to Prevent Fires and Fatal Incidents in Industry

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Daily fires and fatalities, incidents and accidents - is the land-sliding of a nation's as well as companies' safety culture requiring immediate reviews to act upon with innovative interventions. Safety culture approach and methodology of corporates is fragmented, not focused; reactive, not proactive; probable, not precise. Most of the Top managements play proxies of safety culture, not real or in action. Immediate abatement of workplace risks is of utmost importance, as the lack of safety measures leads to organisational stress and burnout. Organisational restructuring of safety culture for business sustainability needs an attempt by the corporates. Conducting safety culture at the levels with simplicity and intensity is important to see the effects and their positive consequences. More than languages, affectionate voices, as in family, are important. Reasons why some companies succeed and others struggle with safety culture development? Controlling unsafe / at-risk behaviours is important, but more important are organisational issues that impact safety culture development. Safety culture is not only organisational behaviour management but it is human performance improvement (HPI). There are people in organisations who lobby against safety culture for different reasons, and some people, on the other hand, push the same to another level. Engage the government on the subject of safety culture so that every corporation has to sustain it for saving lives and businesses. Corporate safety should not be an event management but a think tank for constant action. Invite industry-renowned mentors for innovating company's safety culture. Safety professionals of some companies struggle too much when directors and top leadership don't value Safety, and then safety doesn't become part of the daily culture of their company. Production targets often supersede people's safety in such companies. A strong Safety culture is the defence wall against all odds in business sustainability/losses. Every company, every individual goes through both safe as well as at-risk behaviours, every festival wishes only safe behaviours for our colleagues irrespective of caste, colour or creed. Let's promise that we shall make this planet safe and comfortable forever for each other. In order to prevent fires and fatalities, building positive organisations would require human performance improvements, which can be achieved by implementations of the Total Safety Culture (TSC) Interventions and scoping BBS actions for its cultural enrichment, depth, quality and update. Organisational demography of safety culture is vital in effectively preventing fires, fatalities and incidents.

Keywords: Safety, culture, fires, fatalities, industry, challenges, strategies, HPI, BBS

Introduction, Relevance and Theoretical Background

Most companies care for profits and money more than the safety of their human resources. Most of the companies' managements and employers do not decide to spend on safety cultural aspects, as because they are less sensitive or not concerned towards unsafe way of working leading to incidents, impact on new generations, disaster, family suffering, gas leakages or they are not aware that the benefits of safety implementation in any company, small or big, would definitely outweigh the monetary gains of not implementing it.

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While considering the economics of safety management approach, it is vital to understand why companies stop and refresh their actions for programs leading to long-term safety culture (Kaila & Group, 2021).

Global fire incidents directly cause approximately 50,000 deaths and 170,000 injuries annually, and the indirect fire casualties could be more. Fire incidents are widely classified into four types: building, outdoor fires, vegetation and vehicle (Shi et al., 2025). India's rapid industrialization came at a significant human cost, with workplace safety emerging as one of the nation's most pressing public health crises. According to data compiled till December 10, 2024, workplace accidents resulted in 400 fatalities and more than 850 serious injuries. The industries face alarming safety challenges like the occupational diseases that include musculoskeletal injuries, silicosis, lung diseases, byssinosis, asbestosis, pesticide poisoning and so on across different sectors, due to failures in regulatory enforcement and corporate responsibility. Government policies have eased workplace inspections and licensing rules to encourage business growth. It prioritizes ease of doing business over worker safety. DGFASLI report in India indicated that there were 32,413 industrial accidents in 2020 that led to 1,050 deaths and 3,882 injuries. The workforce faced challenges like physical hazards affecting 97.5% of agricultural workers, mechanical hazards (50%) and biological hazards (19.7%). Despite the national policy on

occupational safety and health introduced in 2009, implementation is still lacking due to challenges of an unorganised workforce, the low-cost labor, limited public health funds, and shortage of occupational safety and health (OSH) professionals. Action is required to prioritize worker safety, enhance workplace inspections, and strengthen regulatory frameworks to prevent this epidemic from claiming more lives (Dhar et al., 2025).

Positive safety culture is an extra edge for businesses. Total safety culture for human performance improvement (Table 1) is a systematic approach to securing better performance from people. HPI identifies work, worker and workplace performance factors and designs appropriate solutions to deal with them. Continuous 'peer observation and feedback' not only fosters a culture of ongoing development but also aligns employee objectives with organisational goals in real-time, enhancing overall productivity and job satisfaction. The move toward continuous feedback represents not just a trend but a fundamental rethinking of how performance is

managed, with the potential to significantly enhance both individual and organisational success in the modern workplace (Kaila, 2020).

Human Performance is not only carved by how individuals behave in an organisation, but importantly, how an organisation behaves towards those individuals at sites or plants. It is an outcome of interactions between both. HPI means to diagnose organisational performance problems/ gaps and design actions for human performance improvement (HPI) as part of company's culture, Psychological Safety and shared values. The foundation of all human performance is behavioural and organisational positive leadership and safety culture, which must be monitored on measurable and definable monthly trends to check improvements. HPI is a validated tool as an employee performance observation and feedback process at office as well as shop floors for implementation, and it is to be circulated as a company-wide SOP. HODs and top leadership must take performance rounds to the field for daily HPI observation (Kaila, 2022).

Table 1

Human Performance Improvements Require Total Safety Culture (TSC) Interventions

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- Robust Safety systems: reinforcing antecedents for managing all safety issues such as barriers, resources, and safety controls.
 - Safety culture: long term behavioural interventions with fast-tracking action plan.
 - Psychological safety: do people feel psychologically safe?
 - Human factors of safety: do people feel very strained with occupational stresses, workload, and decision latitude issues?
 - Human error in safety: human cognition, decision making, fear, and pressure. How companies handle group conflicts and differences that delay safety culture decisions.
 - Cultural safety and competency: do people feel understood with their cultural background and beliefs, and how companies respond to these factors effectively?
 - Digitalising safety measures, AI, machine learning, and more innovations
 - Integrating and Reviews by the topmost leaders on all the above interventions.
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Most corporates aimed for HPI as under (Personal Communications, 2025):

- Human performance improvement from a risk management and organisation development (OD) perspective
 - Human Performance Improvement as the Key to Sustainable Safety Excellence
 - Strengthening decision-making at both site execution and office planning levels
 - Identifying systemic human performance gaps and evaluating accountabilities
 - Implementing sustainable improvements through HPI principles
 - Shifting from individual blame to systemic learning
 - Addressing decision quality across operational and strategic domains
 - Ensuring consistency in skills, processes, and culture throughout the project lifecycle
 - Driving transformational change in how we learn from incidents
- Additionally, addressing key challenges in your current decision-making landscape, including:
- Fragmented decision ownership across departments and project phases
 - Inconsistent application of project management standards across regions

- Limited integration of safety governance at leadership levels
- Cultural inertia that hinders proactive learning and cross-functional collaboration

Research Gap and Objectives of the Study

The daily fires and fatalities in our society and Industry are not entirely understood despite the fact that they have significant implications on workers' safety and health. There is a significant research gap concerning the precise effects of fires and fatalities. Objectives are:

- To explore why the fires and fatalities are an almost daily affair in society and Industry.
- To understand challenges and strategies to prevent such daily fires and fatalities.

Method

Many companies participated in this research program, namely, Oil India, Gharda Chemicals, BESAFE, SEIL, ThyssenKrupp, DCM Shriram, Vardhman, Idex, Thermax, Jindal, AFCONS, ONGC, NSCI, IIM, Hindalco, IOCL, KAPL, Tata Projects, L&T, GAIL, SAIL, and HPCL. This article is an extract from a longitudinal national safety culture program, and this research was conducted over a year during 2024-25 in India including 600 Health, Safety, Environment (HSE) professionals/experts from diverse industry

sectors including 12 organisations. Mixed methods approach was used and data were drawn from official records, literature reviews, eye witnesses, lunch meetings, site-based trainings, surveys, interviews, field insights, questionnaires, plant visits, lunch/dinner conversations with operational staffs, experts' meetings, national seminars, post-session meetings, informal conversations, emails, tele-meetings, video conferences, and recommendations. Presentations and discussions focused on improving safety culture to meet the research objectives. Random sampling design was followed for selection of sample across industry from diverse sectors such as chemicals, construction, steel, gas, petroleum, energy, pharmaceutical from MNCs, public/private sectors. This paper is an extract of a national research program of the Forum of Behavioural Safety under Bharat Bane Surakshit (BBS) mission (Kaila, 2025). The study results and implications are reflected below from a rigorous review of safety culture literature and experiences / case studies shared by industry leaders mainly from the Indian organisations.

Results and Discussion

It was made to explore why the fires and fatalities are an almost daily affair in society and industry, and to understand its challenges and strategies to prevent such daily fires and fatalities. Corporates that do not have an organisational base for their safety culture keep suffering from incidents. Companies that possess a strong safety culture exhibited higher rates of safety protocol implementation, reduced accident occurrences, and enhanced overall safety outcomes depending upon management commitment, employee engagement, resource availability and consistent enforcement of safety measures. Companies must focus on developing a robust safety culture by emphasising continuous safety training, ensuring management commitment, involving employees and conducting regular assessments of safety practices to determine effective strategies for promoting a positive safety culture within the industry (Anzagira et al., 2025).

Culture of safety means humanity, humanism, humanistic behaviourism and business ethics. Corporates' management must understand that businesses are safe only when workers are safe in industry or elsewhere. Business sustainability cannot be achieved without ensuring robust measures for the life safety of workers. The industry professionals felt that most organisations are slow in developing a safety culture and wait until serious incidents occur. However, there is no easy or single solution for this. The managers must be sensitised by their HOD about this serious flaw. From this qualitative survey, five themes emerged, such as corporations are struggling to build a safety culture, organisations are slow in developing a safety culture, difficulties in enhancing safety culture implementation, understanding the challenges of psychological safety and major concerns of safety culture mentors. Organisations must speed up developing a safety culture and avoid any serious incidents, considering as following: Safety culture is a confusion or fusion of subcultures in business scenarios, seven aspects of Behaviour Based Safety (BBS) 2.0 culture, Human error or cultural failure, safety culture improvements, gaps management and seniors often make employees feel psychologically down. The day corporates act on safety incidents, taking it as a non-negotiable case, safety will certainly be at the level that we all have been waiting to see. Zero tolerance for at-risk behaviours is lacking, and building a safety culture is a struggle throughout. When everyone at the workplace gets trained and behaves as an active observer of at-risk behaviour and corrects it on the spot, a company achieves a total safety culture in a true sense. When seniors make employees feel psychologically down, they don't feel like participating in any safety culture transformation program. Coaching for leadership is required for promoting a positive work culture. Most importantly, BBS culture must be an important element in all safety audits and curriculums (Kaila, 2023, 2025a).

The results of this research are grouped under following 17 themes as HPI Challenges (Table 2).

Table 2

HPI Challenges and Strategies to Prevent Daily Fires and Fatalities in Industry

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- Safety culture approach and methodology of corporates is fragmented, not focused; reactive not proactive; probable not precise.
 - Let's promise that we shall make this planet safe and comfortable ever for each other.
 - Every company, every individual goes through both safe as well as at-risk behaviours, every festival wishes only safe behaviours for our colleagues irrespective of caste, colour or creed.
 - Most of the Top managements play proxies of safety culture, not real or in action.
 - Immediate abatement of workplace risks is utmost important, as lack of safety measures lead to organisational stresses and burnout.
 - Organisational restructuring of safety culture for business sustainability needs an attempt by the corporates.
 - Conducting safety culture down the levels with simplicity and intensity is important to see the effects and their positive consequences.
 - In teaching safety cultures, more than languages, affectionate voices as in family, are important.
 - Reasons why some companies succeed and others struggle for safety culture development?
 - Controlling unsafe / at-risk behaviours are important, but more important are organisational issues that impact safety culture development
 - Safety culture is not only organisational behaviour management but it is human performance improvement (HPI).
 - There are people in organisations who lobby against safety culture for different reasons, and some persons, on the other hand, push the same to another level.
 - Engage the government on the subject of safety culture so that every corporate has to sustain it for saving lives and businesses.
 - Corporate safety should not be an event management but a think tank for constant action.
 - Invite industry renowned mentors for innovating company's safety cultures.
 - Safety professionals of some companies struggle too much when directors and top leadership don't value Safety, and then the safety doesn't become part of the daily culture of their company. Production targets often supersede people's safety in such companies.
 - A strong Safety culture is the defence wall to all odds in business sustainability/losses.
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Organisational hierarchical structure limits safety voices. Behavioural Safety cultures resolve and dissolve all hierarchical structure as everyone is observer to save company from losses and people from injuries. Possible solution: Say 6 -8 observations (in local language) of some independent competent audit agency or management Committee can be put on computer screen, where improvement in safe behaviours is required to seek agreement of staff. No names, they simply click 'Yes' voluntarily. It can be analysed time to time for feedback/improvement. New observations can be put after some period (Kaila, 2023b).

Safety culture must reflect the values of any organisation. Protection of workers against harm and sickness is a fundamental human right, irrespective of where the individual works. Most workplace safety and health research concentrates on the industrial and formal or corporate work settings, very less on the informal sector. Safety behaviour is positively related to safety performance, and safety culture is a better predictor of safety performance than safety behaviour in light of the socio-cultural sub-system model (Asamani, 2020). Safety culture must reflect the nature of any organisation and its manpower because everyone has a right to life and safety, not to get injured or fatal while at work.

An organisation's culture and safety culture are not separate entities. Safety culture is the product and an outcome of an organisation culture and examination of the interrelationship between culture and safety in organisations demonstrates that organisational relationships influence both culture and safety and that effective two-way communication is pivotal to the success of the development of a corporate safety culture. Researches show that organisational culture, competence and work environment have a positive effect on Occupational Safety and Health Occupational and safety behaviour of Employees (Hermanto et al., 2023). Organisational culture and safety culture are still being debated about the exact meaning of the concepts of organisational culture and safety culture, including the interdependent relationships between

them, as well as defining the safety culture and its characteristics, stating the integration of the safety culture in the general culture of the organisations (Lordache & Darabont, 2023).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Fundamentally, the definition of safety culture between managers and workers differs. For managers, it is cost-cutting, production-safety conflicts, and zero-harm; for workers, it is life, injury-free life. Recommendations (Table 3) are concluded below as preventive HPI strategies based on the research findings in order to combat the challenges of fires and fatality incidents in industry.

Behaviour-based Safety Implementation can Help the Industry

BBS is a globally tested behaviour science tool for developing a positive safety culture for organisations. It is never too late and always a good idea for organisation's leadership choosing a planned long-term positive safety and work culture over fires and fatalities, and save people and plants for achieving better economy. This can be fast-tracked as follows, by conducting two hours brief to top management, three hours interaction with site heads, one day practical training with site safety culture steering team, monthly progress tracking on behavioural trends, and quarterly monitoring by company Directors. Focus is on behaviour and barriers at site, not the outcomes. Positive thought and appropriate direction are needed to keep plant safe with a BBS observation time commitment of 5 minutes daily for every person on site (Kaila, 2025).

Merely focusing on behavioural corrections would not provide a totally safe environment unless the situational factors such as engineering updations, resources, and barriers are also taken care of. A multi-national company that made behavioural intervention an 'umbrella for safety culture' and did not improve the site situations suffered fatal incidents as a result (Kaila, 2023a).

Table 3

HPI Recommendations to Combat Challenges of Fires and Fatalities in Industry

- BBS implementation can help the industry, as behaviour is the basis of HPI
- A strong Safety culture is the defence against all odds in business sustainability
- Organisational hierarchical structure limits safety voices
- Most of the Top managements play proxies of safety culture, not real or in action
- Real safety culture goes to the depths of at-risk behaviours.
- Safety culture must reflect the values of any organisation.
- People wish to receive maximum sense of psychological safety.
- An organisation culture and safety culture are not separate entities.
- Managements look for assessments and effectiveness of positive safety culture.
- Building positive organisations is the key to human performance improvements.
- Demography of organisational safety culture is vital to understand its effectiveness
- Scope of BBS actions for its cultural enrichment, depth, quality and updation
- Case study - vISION zERO for HPI implementation through BBS

A Strong Safety Culture is the Defence against all Odds in Business Sustainability

Industry leaders such as Sharma, Thakur, and Gupta approved this hypothesis that a strong safety culture is the defence against all odds in business sustainability. They expressed that it's more than just risk

prevention-it builds resilience, trust, and long-term stability in every aspect of the organisation. A strong safety culture makes businesses resilient. When an organisation cultivates this culture, it builds a resilient foundation that protects not only lives but also reputation, productivity, and long-term viability - the very pillars of business sustainability. When safety is ingrained, employees are trained to

identify risks early, respond quickly, and learn from near-misses. This proactive approach transforms potential crises into opportunities for learning and improvement (Personal Communications, 2025).

Action plan for Hindalco unit to strengthen safety culture is as follows:

- Supervisors' BBS Month celebration in coming month.
- Reward maximum employees and workers each month
- Checklist of 12-points to be implemented
- Increase emotional care through dialogue with working crew
- Video on Hindalco BBS- share with all in monthly training
- Conversation mandatory in BBS after at-risk behaviour correction
- Reverse conversation (repeat by observer)
- Risk based conversation (RBC)
- Reactive safety culture to be minimise
- Quality of observers to increase
- Psychological safety to be enhanced
- Develop both positive safety culture and positive organisation
- Details about BBS observation Data:
 - How many Observers are doing BBS?
 - Number of Observers doing BBS on daily basis?
 - Any Audit programme for BBS Audits?
 - Percentage Increase in BBS Safety Index with respect to previous year
 - Frequency of Monitoring of BBS Data by CEO & Plant Head Weekly/Monthly/Yearly
 - Campaigns / Initiatives taken up for persisting Hot spots (More than 3 months)

Most of the Top managements play proxies of safety culture, not real or in action. Is it true or false? According to Sharma, Director-EHS, "it is false as true leadership demonstrates values in their actions. One who plays proxies is not a leader in the true sense". Nagareddy (Personal Communications, 2025) stated that in the case of Toyota, it's not true, Toyota's Top management is committed to safety, It's more than policy, it's a core value here. Sanjeev Kalkal is of the view that in the present scenarios, the top management is serious about safety. However, many senior industry professionals strongly doubt the ethical and safety behaviours of top management today. In their words, the top management do not know the real value of the safety of their own people. But we, as a safety team, need to proactively do more and more to change the scenarios, Sanjay Hathmode emphasized. Deore (Personal Communications, 2025) observed that many top Management often prioritize appearances over actual implementation when it comes to safety culture. They publicly champion safety initiatives and policies, but fail to provide adequate resources or support for their effective implementation. They conduct superficial audits and assessments, focusing on compliance rather than genuine risk mitigation. They use safety as a marketing tool, highlighting achievements and certifications without addressing underlying issues. They punish whistle-blowers or employees who report safety concerns, rather than encouraging a culture of transparency or accountability (Kaila, 2024).

Real Safety Culture Goes to the Depths of At-risk Behaviours

The pervasive issue of occupational safety poses a compelling

challenge within the global workforce causing a staggering amount of yearly injuries and fatalities worldwide. The research revealed a common oversight in recognising the multidimensional nature of risk perception considered both its deliberative (perceived probability & severity of incurring a hazards' negative consequences) and affective (emotional reactions associated with the hazard) dimensions. A majority of studies found a significant positive association between risk perception and safety behaviours. Individual factors (attitudes) and organisational factors (safety climate) were explored as potential mediators with mixed outcomes, while group and leadership factors were largely neglected. Enhancing the understanding of both deliberative and affective dimensions of risk perception is essential for developing effective training programs to improve safety behaviours (Priolo et al., 2025). Real safety culture must go to the depths of at-risk behaviours in terms of organisational dynamics and barriers to safety implementation.

People Wish to Receive a Maximum Sense of Psychological Safety

People wish to receive a maximum sense of psychological safety but they don't tend to give in the same proportion to others. As organisations navigate the complexities of the global market, understanding and fostering psychological safety within teams has become imperative. In the fast-paced environment of contemporary workplaces, effective team communication stands out as a critical factor for organisational success. At the heart of such communication dynamics lies the concept of psychological safety - a shared belief within teams that encourages individuals to express themselves without fear of negative consequences. Psychological safety is now undergoing a paradigm shift in human resource (HR) practices, which traditionally concentrated on recruitment, training, and performance management. Psychological safety, defined as the perceived safety of interpersonal interaction, influences team communication and performance significantly. Various factors such as role-based characteristics, organisational trust, and empowering leadership contribute to its establishment. Trust moderates the relationship between work locus of control and psychological safety. Training interventions and individualized attention from managers have also been identified as means to enhance psychological safety, especially in inter-professional teams where it is crucial for effective communication and decision-making. Within psychologically safe teams, members feel empowered to voice opinions, share ideas, and challenge norms without fear of reprisal. This openness fosters a culture of constructive feedback and continuous improvement, driving innovation and problem-solving initiatives. HR practices must adapt to foster psychological safety in virtual teams, to promote inclusivity and mitigate communication barriers (Paulus, 2023).

Managements Look for Assessments and Effectiveness of Positive Safety Culture

Proactive approaches are being developed to prevent accidents at work and to evaluate the effectiveness of a positive safety culture and awareness in preventing workplace accidents. With increasing industrialisation, occupational accidents and diseases continue to be a significant global problem. The cause of this problem is often human rather than technical. Strengthening the psychological, behavioural, and structural dimensions of a positive workplace safety culture improves employees' awareness of occupational

safety and health and their proactive behaviour. The impact of a positive safety culture and safety awareness on employee attitudes and their role in reducing unsafe conditions and behaviours must be investigated. Continuous training, management involvement, and effective communication play a crucial role in establishing the effectiveness of a positive safety culture (Gur, 2025).

Ten Actions to focus on long-term positive behavioural safety culture effectiveness :

- Identify observable performance gaps through internal discussions with all departments
- Design performance observations checklist
- Conduct workshops for all departments HODs for HPI implementation
- Develop HPI monitoring team of top management
- Monitor monthly performance improvement
- Developing HPI teams down the levels
- Reward best performing HPI teams every month
- Everyone in the organisation shall be trained as a performance observer for daily observation
- Organisation shall inform all stakeholders that their performance shall be monitored daily.
- HPI shall be a part of company directors' review each month/quarter.

Building Positive Organisations is the Key to Human Performance Improvements

Organisations are under pressure to build and sustain competitive advantage with and through people. For that reason, managers continue to demand results from workers and look for as many ways as possible to increase productivity and decrease the costs of doing business. Human performance improvement (HPI) is a systematic approach to securing better performance from people. HPI is not a tool reserved exclusively for training and development practitioners. Anyone can use it, including managers, supervisors, and employees to improve human performance (Rothwell et al., 2018). Building a positive organisation is the key to human performance improvement. Figure 1 reflects that human performance improvements help prevent fires and fatalities by implementation of positive safety culture interventions (Kaila, 2024a).

Figure 1

Model Framework of Prevention towards Fires and Fatalities in Organisations

Demography of Organisational Safety Culture is Vital to Understand its Effectiveness

When contractors staff are maximum at workplaces, their active involvement in safety culture movement is very vital, if not taken into consideration by organisations, as it is, would not provide protection and care to the manpower for saving them from injuries and fatalities. Organisations must underline this for their sustainability. Workers know the real safety culture at the ground level more than the managers. In reality, most companies did not involve workmen in the implementation of safety behaviours, hence

the safety incidents do not subside (Kaila, 2025).

At-risk behaviours or barriers to safety culture exist at workplaces indicates that the whole system or management is in favour of these unsafe activities happening, which is part of an accident culture leading to incidents and accidents. It's a serious cultural failure. Actions must be taken accordingly in spirit by all concerned from top to bottom with 'Dharma and Karma'. Four directors of a chemical plant, while reviewing the safety culture program stated that it needs to be implemented from ourselves to our shop-floors by self-empowerment and empowering others in daily activities at home or road driving. Safety is like, you are holding a rock, if you leave, it would fall on you. Safety culture actions must be reviewed by the unit heads by connect and care principles. Check the most negligible points, respect the lowest level worker, safety documents must be field-tested, verbal instructions must transform into employees behavioural pattern to documentation and reviews. All must work with company objectives for business sustainability. Company conflicts between production, maintenance, and safety costs must be resolved at the earliest, as accident price to all concerned is quite big (Personal Communications, 2025).

Scope of BBS Actions for its Cultural Enrichment, Depth, Quality and Updation

Our organisations have still not developed Caring as a corporate value, they are reactive not positive, not empathetic, not conversational, hence the risk is just corrected, not communicated.

Industrial professionals state that employees are not feeling psychologically safe to voice their issues. They are just grieving for mental health issues for which they are not finding solutions. Supervisors need to ask workmen how to improve situations for safety, who have ample points that can be very significant to practice safety at workplaces. People conduct observations just mechanically, not by heart, but for compliance or target completion. So, gaps remain and incidents continue. 70-75% industry is manned by contract persons who are hardly trained that become the source of incidents. Training is given up to managers but not supervisors or frontline workmen. So, the risk is not getting controlled. Safety culture has flown halfway into organisations which have developed its skeleton or structure but not its skin and blood. So the oxygen is less to rejuvenate energies. The good change is that the managers are being present on the shop-floors, and the workmen are exposed to multiple locations, so managers must consult them for human potential improvements (HPI). Awareness, along with daily shop-floor conversations on safety culture can strengthen beliefs of employees. Long-term handholding as well as guidance is needed for organisations to integrate the cultural transformation for which the BBS scope of work is listed (Table 4) for its cultural enrichment, depth, quality and updation. Management, directors, employees, workmen, and stakeholders together can make safety culture. It is important for organisations that the safety culture slowdown is very serious for leading to incidents. Hence, companies must not be complacent in fast-tracking their safety culture actions.

Considering human performance improvements as the key, corporates must understand the challenges and implement strategies for preventing daily fires and fatalities by certain well researched actions such as behaviour based safety implementation for building strong safety culture for business sustainability, limiting organisational hierarchical structure, top managements to stop playing proxies of safety culture, addressing depths of at-risk

behaviours, reflecting safety culture in the values of an organisation, ensuring that people receive maximum sense of psychological safety, integrating safety culture in the organisational culture, ensuring assessments for effectiveness of positive safety culture,

addressing the demographic participation of organisation-wide safety culture to understand its effectiveness, and maximising the scope of BBS actions for its cultural enrichment, depth, quality and updation (Largier & Merle, 2024).

Table 4

BBS Scope of Work and Actions

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- First HOD get trained and then develop employees as observers.
 - Second stage - Reach out to all supervisors so that they further develop workmen as observers.
 - Increase quality of observers to observe 12-behaviours with 12-Ps (eyes for safety/voice for safety).
 - Spot-correction of at-risk behaviours must follow with risk based conversations (RBC) by observers.
 - Connect with workmen, not control is the mantra for risk based conversations.
 - Reactive culture must stop to adopt independent/interdependent safety culture.
 - Quantity of observers to reach last person as trained observer.
 - Introducing innovations /concepts like psychological safety, human factors, human error
 - Reverse TBT to be adopted by all front-line people.
 - Goal is to transform as a Positive organisation which is a must for positive safety culture.
 - HODs to track observers accountability along with area/section incharges.
 - BBS training must continue through supervisors to integrate it into cultural practice.
 - Observers to be empowered as QSHEW observers.
 - Reward program for observers.
 - BBS culture from workplace to anyplace, from self to shop-floor for its sustainability.
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Case Study - vISION zERO for HPI Implementation through BBS

This report of Behavioural-based safety (BBS) training conducted at KAPL Chiplun on 18 Nov 2025 narrates the active involvement of top management in designing and implementation steps of safety culture for controlling and preventing accidents, incidents, fires, and fatalities.

The meeting started at 09.15 am with grace of President B.K. Dutta. He graced the session with a strong intent to promote a culture of learning and accountability. He personally oversaw the entire program and remained present throughout the day, which significantly motivated the participants. His presence set the tone for the meeting, encouraging everyone to take the discussions seriously, remain attentive, and note down all key observations shared during the session. Padmanabhan further set the tone for the program by sharing insights from his extensive experience of 12 years of service with BPCL in Mumbai, followed by 2 years in London and 4 years in Guwahati. Having handled major refinery operations, his technical depth and practical understanding were evident throughout his interaction. He has an exceptional clarity in communication and a highly practical approach to every discussion. His words and demeanour inspired the entire KAPL trainee team and reinforced the importance of adopting Behaviour-Based Safety practices with sincerity and ownership. Then 9.45 am Kaila, the training mentor a world-renowned organisational psychologist as a pioneer of BBS took forwards the discussion.

Key Takeaways from the Session the training mentor: the training mentor shared several powerful insights that significantly enriched the understanding of Behaviour-Based Safety (BBS) and its relevance to organisational culture. One of his core messages was that safety culture is fundamental to the overall culture of any organisation. He initiated a reflective journey focused on empowering every level of the workforce-whether plant operators, shop-floor workers, or employees in office and administrative roles.

He emphasized that it is the responsibility of seniors and colleagues to ensure that juniors or subordinates are capable of carrying forward their work safely and effectively. The mentor explained that BBS builds awareness, and awareness leads to alertness. He illustrated this through several industry examples, such as the HPCL initiative called 'SATARK', which he helped establish. He interpreted BBS as "Big Brother Safety", and in another terms in Hindi, as "Baccho Bachao Suraksha", emphasizing mutual care and vigilance. One of the most impactful analogies he shared was from psychology: just as a sample of blood represents the entire blood culture of the body, a sample of behaviour from one part of the plant reflects the overall plant culture. This clarified the importance of consistent safe behaviour across all departments.

The training mentor narrated multiple successful safety interventions from leading organisations:

GAIL Project- The Project Director introduced a monthly award for the Best Observer, encouraging proactive observation and safe behaviour.

Toyota- He initiated the "I-Care" program to reinforce safety ownership.

SEIL (Singapore)- Promoted a culture where "Everybody will speak for safety for each other."

Bayer Crop Science- Implemented the 3R Framework: Review, Reward, and Reinforcement.

He also encouraged KAPL to observe November as the BBS Month and suggested celebrating 18th November as BBS Day, to reinforce commitment and build long-term awareness.

Stages of Safety Culture Maturity: the training mentor elaborated on the four progressive stages of safety culture maturity:

- *Reactive Safety Culture*: blaming, fault-finding, stop the work, snatching gate pass, shouting, issuing warning letter, are some behaviours of the reactive safety culture, which is the worst culture.
- *Dependent Safety Culture*: Safety is driven by external rules,

supervision, and compliance. Employees follow safety procedures mainly to avoid penalties. Responsibility lies primarily with management.

- *Independent Safety Culture*: Employees begin to take individual responsibility for their own safety. They understand the personal impact of their actions and maintain safe practices even without supervision.
- *Interdependent Safety Culture*: The most mature stage, where safety becomes a shared value. Employees watch out for one another, provide constructive feedback, and work collectively to improve safety. Trust, teamwork, and proactive hazard control are strong in this stage.

Role of Behaviour-Based Safety (BBS): The training mentor highlighted that BBS is a critical tool to help organisations transition from a rule-driven (dependent) culture to a self-driven and mutually responsible (independent & interdependent) safety culture. BBS focuses on observing day-to-day behaviours, analysing unsafe acts, providing timely feedback, Reinforcing safe practices through positive encouragement. When implemented properly and integrated with broader safety management systems, BBS fosters a proactive environment where employees feel empowered to identify hazards, correct risky behaviours, and strengthen overall resilience. At 12.30 pm, everyone went for plant visit for 30 minutes observations to identify unsafe behaviours.

Compilation of Data and BBS Scoring: After the plant visit, all participants submitted their observations in a structured data format. Using these inputs, the team calculated the BBS Score and classified the findings into key parameters: Number of Safe Behaviours, Number of At-Risk Behaviours, Number of Spot Corrections, and Required Steering Team Actions. This classification helped create a clear picture of the existing safety behaviour patterns within the plant and identified areas requiring immediate or long-term improvement.

Team Categorisation and Action Planning: The training mentor then divided participants into plant-wise groups and facilitated a discussion on developing an effective Action Plan for BBS Implementation. Each team was encouraged to identify: Priority behaviours that need correction, Opportunities for strengthening safe practices, Methods for observation, documentation, and feedback, Roles and responsibilities for each member in the BBS journey. The exercise helped participants internalize the importance of proactive behaviour and collective responsibility.

Train-the-Trainer Initiative (TTT): Another major initiative highlighted during the session was a TTT model. The idea is to empower selected employees from each plant or department who can: Undergo deeper BBS training, train other colleagues across departments, ensure consistency in behavioural observation practices, and support sustainable safety culture development within KAPL. This model aims to build internal capability, reduce dependency on external resources, and make BBS a self-driven, continuous process across the organisation. Finally, the whole KAPL team took BBS Pledge.

Closing Session of the Behaviour-Based Safety (BBS) Training: the KAPL President, Mr. Datta provided an overall summary of the training program. He highlighted how management goals and BBS principles can be integrated and aligned with daily routines, emphasizing that continuous observation, immediate correction, and collective participation are critical to sustaining a robust safety

culture. Director, Mr. Padmanabhan addressed the topic of conflicts that may arise during BBS implementation. He illustrated with examples where differences in perspectives may occur and emphasised that any argument or disagreement should be supported by solid data. He further discussed the importance of open communication, mutual respect, and understanding in resolving differences, and stressed that constructive conflict resolution is essential for team cohesion and effective implementation of BBS initiatives.

Key Observations and Concluding Notes: From my perspective, the Behaviour-Based Safety (BBS) training was highly insightful and highlighted several important aspects: BBS is not limited to a specific month or day; it must be integrated into daily routines and work practices. Safety awareness should be a continuous, proactive effort rather than a periodic exercise. Considering the nature of the materials handled and the complexity of plant operations, it is essential to ensure maximum care for employees and shop-floor workers. BBS is not the responsibility of a single safety officer or plant head, but a collective responsibility that requires participation from everyone at all levels. Interpersonal communication and behaviour with staff and colleagues during daily operations play a crucial role in fostering a safe and supportive work environment. Awareness, observation, and timely corrective actions must become integral to every interaction. The training provided an excellent opportunity to learn from senior officials, interact with plant heads, and gain practical exposure through on-site observation. The experience has been extremely valuable and will contribute significantly to reinforcing a strong safety culture at KAPL, a group of chemical plants.

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